

Envisaging Artificial Intelligence in Indian Digital Army

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Abstract

The very purpose of AI is to preserve and recreate itself without the limitations of the human body. It is an oxymoron. It is guided by imagination. AI demands precision. Digital India, Flagship programme launched by Prime Minister Narendra Modi triggered policymakers to establish AI ready infrastructure by making the country digitally empowered in the field of technology. With rivals being ahead of us, it is of the utmost importance to view AI as a critical element of national security strategy. Elon Musk called the prospect of artificial intelligence “our greatest existential threat” in a 2014 interview with MIT students¹. Unmanned drones furnish sustained surveillance and meteoric strike on targets, and small robots are used to disarm improvised explosive devices. Stone pelting could be a history soon. The defence budget for the year 2018-19 is increased by 7.81 per cent² to meet the operational requirements and research developments to diminish the need for human soldiers to risk their lives. While the industries gen up on AI-research, numerous cyber security start-ups are inculcating AI to tackle the threats. This paper seeks to study the challenges faced by the defence and the public at large to address and adapt to the developments in the field of AI. The study is based on various books, articles and case studies with interpretation. The paper is concluded by highlighting the importance of Rational thinking to make the world a better place.

1. *Observer - Stephen Hawking, Elon Musk, and Bill Gates Warn About Artificial Intelligence by Michael Sainato 08/19/15*

2. *The Economic Times by Shaurya Gurung, ET Bureau, Feb 01, 2018*

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Defence, Cyber Security, Digital India, Infrastructure, Robots, technology.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the computer system designed to perform the tasks of human beings. Klaus Schwab founder and Executive Chairman of World Economic Forum, Geneva says “we stand in the brink of technological revolution that will fundamentally alter the way we live, work, and relate to one another. In its scale, scope, and complexity, the transformation will be unlike anything humankind has experienced before”.

The history of Artificial Intelligence (AI) began in the period of classical, lore and tittle-tattle. As Pamela McCorduck writes, AI began with “an ancient wish to forge the gods.” In the late 1940s and 50s, mathematicians, psychologists, engineers, economists, doctors

began to consider and debate the possibility of creating an artificial brain which was later evolved as an academic discipline. The invention of the Colossus Computer in the 1940s was the result of an attempt to describe the mechanism of human thinking as mechanical manipulation of symbols, a machine based on the abstract essence of mathematical reasoning. This device dramatically triggered scientists to discover the possibility of constructing an electronic brain.

Only in the 21st century when many problems were solved by successfully applying machine learning due to the presence of powerful and effective computer hardware, investment and interest boomed in the field of AI. Observers such as Ray Kurzweil anticipated the forthcoming of artificial general intelligence: a machine with intellectual capabilities that exceed the abilities of human beings.

AI has been used to tackle some of the world's greatest challenges and to develop and advance in numerous fields like optical character recognition, handwriting recognition, speech & face recognition, artificial creativity, computer vision, virtual reality, image processing, photo and video manipulation, diagnosis (artificial intelligence), game artificial intelligence and computer game bot, natural language, processing, translation, semantic web, E-mail spam filtering, robotics, cognitive, cybernetics, developmental robotics (Epigenetic), hybrid intelligent system, intelligent agent, intelligent control, litigation. AI has become a major area of investment. It is estimated that annually worldwide military is spending approximately 7.5 billion USD (in 2015) especially on drones which are capable of autonomous functioning and are classified as assets. In 2017, Vladimir Putin stated that “Whoever becomes the leader in (artificial intelligence) will become the ruler of the world”. Many artificial intelligence researchers seek to distance themselves from military applications of AI as it can be dangerous.

Lee De Forest, inventor of radio device explored the concept and idea of combat drones which was presented through an article and was published in a 1940 publication of popular mechanics. But the modern military drone is the art of John Stuart Foster Jr., a nuclear physicist and former head of the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory who was an aeroplane hobbyist and had a visionary to build weapons. Major invention took place in 1973 when Defence advanced Research project agency (DARPA) built two prototypes called “Prairie” and “Calere” with a modified lawn-mower engine staying aloft for two hours while carrying 28-pound of the load.

Israel launched unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) for real-time surveillance, electronic warfare, and decoys. Visual intelligence provided by UAVs helped Israel to completely counterpoise the Syrian air defences in Operation Mole Cricket 19 at the start of the 1982 Lebanon War, resulting in no pilots downed.

Astonished by the Israel's technological advancement, The US acquired many UAVs. As the UAVs improved, it was deployed in the war for the very first time during the First Gulf war and according to a May 1991 Department of the Navy report: “At least one UAV was airborne at all times during Desert Storm.” After the Gulf War successfully demonstrated their utility, global militaries invested widely in the domestic development of combat UAVs. On October 7, 2001, in Kandahar American UAV murdered a human. in the name of global war on terrorism, USA has conveniently increased its used of drone to attack foreign countries. It is estimated that 6000 and odd people were the victims of the drone attacks in the USA in 5 years.

Death of thousands by the unmanned UAVs caused chaos, moral and legal concerns. Autonomous initiation of attack without human involvement is even more abstract than the use of weapons such as missiles, Aerial bombardment for the reason that there could be a possibility of quick contrast action lacking human sensibility. On the other hand, they reduce casualties of the soldiers. Drones built by the human can be hacked, manipulated, destroyed and misused or there can be an error in the programme, malfunction resulting in disaster and deaths. There are

on-going debates as to whether the attribution of moral responsibility can be apportioned appropriately under existing international humanitarian law, which is based on four principles: military necessity, the distinction between military and civilian objects, prohibition of unnecessary suffering, and proportionality. To overcome the hurdles of hacking, manipulating and to deal with other cyber-crimes and crimes related to AI it is very necessary to have a concrete set of laws. Privacy and confidentiality being major concerns in today's world, many start-up are using AI to tackle issues and to protect the system from aliens.

In India, public flying of drones was prohibited. Government of India Office of The Director General of Civil Aviation on Oct 30th unveiled draft norms for the usage of Ariel vehicles to develop a regulatory framework to safeguard the interest of the people without compromising on the security. Until now, flying drones in India without the permission of concerned authorities was illegal owing to safety concerns.

It is to be noted that it not only takes away life but it affects the mental health of the people alive. UAV operators, controllers experience psychological stress due to combats resulting in posttraumatic stress disorder especially when a death occurs. These psychological conditions can be experienced by civilians who witness and face such wars. In war zones, people avoid gathering at one place and often children are not sent out of house fearing death.

AI is an oxymoron AI is capable of taking life and giving life. AI is prominently used in the medical field to save lives. It gives way for space exploration, reduction of errors, in the field of medical sciences for the purpose of conducting robotic radio surgery; increases work efficiency, faster technological advancement, Delivery of blood, food to the disaster victims, delivery of goods by e-commerce companies, taking the survey, Ariel mapping, damage assessments during natural calamities and makes life easier and convenient. Data, experience, logic, facts and opinion should go through a process of rational thinking for a sound output. It is a trial and error method because of problems with physical concepts of the mind leaves no or little room for free will. Ability to consider the relevant variables of a situation and to approach, collocate, and examine relevant information to arrive at a sound conclusion is the need of the hour.

References

- McCorduck., & Pamela. (2004). *Machines Who Think* (2nd ed.), Natick, MA: A. K. Peters, Ltd., ISBN 1-56881-205-1, OCLC 52197627.
- Kurzweil., Ray. (2005), *The Singularity is Near*, Viking Press, ISBN 0-14-303788-9, OCLC 71826177.
- Clifford., & Catherine. (2017). "In the same way there was a nuclear arms race, there will be a race to build A.I., says tech exec". CNBC.
- "Robot Television Bomber", *Popular Mechanics*, December 1940, pp. 805-806
<https://fas.org/irp/agency/dod/idarma.pdf>
- Azoulai., & Yuval. (2011). "Unmanned combat vehicles shaping future warfare". *Globes*.
- Levinson., Charlesk (2010). "Israeli Robots Remake Battlefield". *The Wall Street Journal*. p. A10.
- UAV evolution – how natural selection directed the drone revolution". 15 November 2012.
- "The Toll Of 5 Years Of Drone Strikes". *The Huffington Post*. 24 January 2014.
- Ed Pilkington. (2015). "Former US military personnel urge drone pilots to walk away from controls".
- Carroll., & Rory. (2012). "*The philosopher making the moral case for US drones*". *The Guardian*. ISSN 0261-3077.
[http://www.dgca.nic.in/misc/draft%20cars/CAR%20-%20UAS%20\(Draft_Nov2017\)](http://www.dgca.nic.in/misc/draft%20cars/CAR%20-%20UAS%20(Draft_Nov2017)).
- World Commission on Environment and Development, *Our Common Future* (1987).